

**WILLEM
BARENTSZ
POLAR
INSTITUTE**

Frigga Kruse

Archaeological fieldwork on Jan Mayen, Norwegian Sea

August 13 – 25, 2014

Final report

Source: Internet.

Non-technical summary

The Royal Netherlands Navy invited scientists of the Willem Barents Polar Institute among others to take part in an expedition to the Arctic island of Jan Mayen in the Greenland Sea between August 13 and August 25, 2014. Among them was an archaeological team of the Arctic Centre of the University of Groningen. Their aim was to investigate changes to the island's cultural heritage over the last 30 years by assessing the heavily eroding material remains of a 17th century whaling station in Kvalrossbukta and by conducting a walkover survey in as many additional bays as possible. They eventually spent three days in Kvalrossbukta and discovered that although threatened by the sea, many indicative remains may yet be found under a thick layer of loose sand that has slid down from the slopes above. They visited Sørbukta, Guineabukta, and Titeltbukta, and although a hint of structures was found in Titeltbukta supported by a handful of century-old Dutch bricks, these finds do not make for a convincing former whaling station at this location. Following their assessment, the team recommend a thorough desk-based assessment to be carried out followed by a timely rescue excavation in Kvalrossbukta.

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Introduction

“The Jan Mayen Expedition 2014 (JM14) is a multidisciplinary expedition based on an out of area readiness activity under arctic conditions. HNLMS ZEELAND (ZLND; Fig. 1) will be used as a platform for scientists and marines for their activities on and ivo Jan Mayen. Due to the wide variety of activities and the scheduled media attention, it is aimed that this expedition will improve the position of the Royal Netherlands Navy in the community.” (Deployment order Jan Mayen Expedition 2014, 9 July 2014)

Fig. 1 HNLMS ZEELAND (left). Source: F. Kruse.

“Partners for this expedition are the Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO), the Royal Dutch Geographic Society (KNAG), and the Willem Barentsz Polar Institute (WBPI), who work with several other institutes and universities.” (Deployment order Jan Mayen Expedition 2014, 9 July 2014)

“By conduction the Jan Mayen Expedition, experiences are gained in working out of area under expeditionary conditions. The multidisciplinary composition of the team offers an opportunity for scientists in a broad spectrum to enhance their knowledge on the arctic and historical studies currently conducted and comparing executed studies. Working together with the Royal Netherlands Navy and scientists provides opportunities for all participants resulting in positive posture towards the society.” (Deployment order Jan Mayen Expedition 2014, 9 July 2014)

“2014 marks the 400th anniversary of the discovery of Jan Mayen and the establishment of the Jan Mayen whaling base. On behalf of the Netherlands, the Royal Netherlands Navy have applied for a permit to celebrate the anniversary in the timeframe 14. – 19. August [actual dates 16. – 21. August]. “ (County Governor of Nordland, 11 July 2014)

“A permit for the memorial service marking the 400th anniversary of the discovery of Jan Mayen is hereby granted to G. J. van den Dam on behalf of the Royal Netherlands Navy. Specifically, the permit approves the following activities:

- Landing with boat [...]
- Camping [...]
- Renovating the memorial rock in Kvalrossbukta
- Archaeological investigations in Kvalrossbukta, Guineabukta, Kokslette, and Jamesonbukta.
- [...]”

(County Governor of Nordland, 11 July 2014)

“Jan Mayen is also home to a number of both new and old cultural heritage artifacts. Several have been restored or maintained and are subsequently in good condition. Most, however, are in poor condition and many are on the verge of disappearing. These are not to be mistaken for rubbish and must be left untouched. Excavation and displacement of cultural heritage artifacts is prohibited by the regulation §4, 1.2.” (County Governor of Nordland, 11 July 2014)

“The last remains of the old whaling station in Kvalrossbukta are situated in a highly erosion prone area. Any traffic in the area is likely to add to the problem. The area is not protected by a walking band, but we strongly request that activity in the area is limited to a minimum in order to preserve these artifacts. A condition to the permit is therefore that excavation and displacement of artifacts is prohibited and that walking around vulnerable artifacts should be limited as much as possible.”

(County Governor of Nordland, 11 July 2014)

Aims and objectives

“Netherlands Maritime Force Maritime Battle Staff (NLMF/MBS) and HNLMS ZEELAND (ZLND) plan and conduct an expedition on and in the vicinity of Jan Mayen (NO) from 11 Aug 14 till 26 Aug 14 [original dates; actual dates 13 Aug 14 till 25 Aug 14] in order to achieve both own training objectives

as well as contribute to the programs developed by scientists on their multidisciplinary research.”

(Deployment order Jan Mayen Expedition 2014, 9 July 2014)

Upon invitation by the Royal Netherlands Navy, the Willem Barentsz Polar Institute, of which the Arctic Centre of the University of Groningen is a member organisation, formulated the following scientific plan:

“Wetenschappelijk doel

1. In kaart brengen van de huidige archeologische en biologische warden op het gehele eiland en deze vergelijken met de complete beschrijvingen die gemaakt zijn in 1983. Dit zal minimaal twee wetenschappelijke publicaties opleveren.
2. Verzamelen van nieuw materiaal, dat na thuiskomst wordt uitgewerkt, als onderdeel van bestaande programma’s op andere locaties. Dit zal minimaal twee publicaties opleveren.
3. Vaststellen van toekomstige mogelijkheden voor projecten.

Overige doelen

4. Aandacht genereren van het algemeen publiek voor het multidisciplinair onderzoek, de 400 jarige geschiedenis van Nederlanders op Jan Mayen (de Rijksuniversiteit Groningen bestaat ook 400 jaar) en deze unieke expeditie als samenwerking tussen marine en poolonderzoekers.
5. Studenten laten kennis maken met poolonderzoek.
6. Ervaring opdoen met multidisciplinaire expedities als voorbereiding op de expeditie naar Oost-Spitsbergen in augustus 2015 met 50 wetenschappers.”

(Wetenschappelijk plan, Arctisch Centrum & WBPI)

With regards to the archaeological potential of the island, two of a total of ten envisaged scientific projects were of interest to the archaeological team:

“Projecten

1. Karteren van archeologische resten van de Nederlandse 17de eeuwse walvisvaarders in Kavlrøssbukta.
2. Kust surveys voor het vaststellen van archeologische resten en aantallen zeevogels. Langslopen van stranden en kliffen. Tellen en karteren.”

(Wetenschappelijk plan, Arctisch Centrum & WBPI)

The archaeological team were:

- Louwrens Hacquebord (Arctic Centre, Groningen), geographer and archaeologist, specialist on 17th century whaling in the Arctic
- Peter Jordan (Arctic Centre, Groningen), archaeologist, director of the Arctic Centre
- Frigga Kruse (Arctic Centre, Groningen), archaeologist, specialist in ecological impacts of human activities, experience in Arctic mapping
- Frits Steenhuisen (Arctic Centre, Groningen), environmental scientists, experience in mercury and POP pollution, experience in Arctic fieldwork and mapping
- Marthe Koeweiden (Groningen Institute of Archaeology), archaeology student, desk top studies

Fig. 2 The archaeological team from left to right: Frits Steenhuisen, Louwrens Hacquebord, Peter Jordan, Frigga Kruse, and Marthe Koeweiden. Source: S. Barr.

On invitation of Prof. Hacquebord, Susan Barr of the Directorate for Cultural Heritage of Norway also joined the expedition. She oversaw and commented on the plans and activities of the archaeological team.

Based on the above aims and objectives, the archaeological team listed some general and daily objectives, which the Royal Netherlands Navy incorporated into the Deployment Order (Appendix 1, A1.1; original dates were used as opposed to actual ones). These objectives were aimed at high flexibility yet maximum research output. The archaeological team hoped to achieve this by being dropped at Kvalrossbukta and using this as a base for three days. They further envisaged a transfer to Sørbukta and a walkover survey of neighbouring bays on the fourth day.

Methodology

“[...] ZLND will sail from Den Helder to Jan Mayen. Upon arrival, a meeting will be set up on the station at Jan Mayen, while subsequently the coxwains will execute some beach recces and the ZLND will collect a sonar buoy ivo 71.15N, 7.7W. Upon completion, all units will return to ZLND for the preparations of their activities. Weather depending, all activities will be de-conflicted to provide all participants as much time as possible. Weather depending, ZLND will primarily support TNO at sea ivo the sonar buoy, whilst others execute their activities on Jan Mayen. The station on Jan Mayen will act as fallback for medical support and shelter. During this 5-day expedition, a social will be held for the residents of the Jan Mayen station and the crew. After 5 days of activities, ZLND will return [via Bergen] to Den Helder.” (Deployment order Jan Mayen Expedition 2014, 9 July 2014)

Phasing [actual dates]

Phase 0 – Planning and preparation

Phase 1 – Deployment 13 – 16 Aug 14

Phase 2 – Execution 16 – 21 Aug 14

Phase 3 – Redeployment 21 – 25 Aug 14

Phase 0 – Planning and preparation

Further to the archaeological schedule mentioned above (Appendix 1, A1.1), the author feels it necessary to refer to and append the archaeological equipment list (A1.2), the camping and cooking equipment (A.1.3) as well as the team’s expedition food (A1.4). These are deemed useful to relate in light of possible future archaeological expeditions to the Arctic island. Hand-written annotations highlight the (lack of) functionality of specific items.

Saturday, August 16, 2014

Upon arrival in Båtvika (see Appendix 2 for maps of all locations mentioned in this text), the marines and the scientists received the environmental briefing from the Norwegian station commander. The archaeological team was thereafter transferred by car to Kvalrossbukta. The team’s activities were recorded in the photographic record and index provided in Appendix 3.

In the evening, Louwrens Hacquebord and Susan Barr led the team on a reconnaissance of the former whaling station. They were accompanied and filmed by the media team. Hacquebord, Barr, and the media then left. The archaeological team continued with a walkover, using yellow survey flags to mark anything of archaeological or other interest (Fig. 3). The survey flags proved a very

useful tool indeed. Meanwhile, Frits Steenhuisen choose a widely visible location to set up the differential GPS (dGPS) and tested the connection between the base and the rover. This worked fine.

Fig. 3 At the former whaling station in Kvalrossbukta, yellow survey flags were used to mark points of interest. Source: F. Kruse.

Sunday, August 17, 2014

Peter Jordan had left the team to join Louwrens Hacquebord on a walk to Titeltbukta. Frits Steenhuisen was incapacitated in the morning. Frigga Kruse and Marthe Koeweiden therefore began the day's activities alone.

Fig. 4 An example of the material remains on the slopes above the site. Source: F. Kruse.

Instead of walking along the beach towards the site, they choose to walk along the rapidly eroding slope of volcanic sand in order to examine the material remains here (Fig. 4). On site, they investigated the rockfaces above the slopes. They thereby encountered possible archaeological remains and decided to conduct a metal detector survey in Area 1 of the site.

For the metal detector survey, a grid was laid out that entirely excluded the cobble beach but that included the sandy slope up to the rockface. Frigga Kruse operated at her own risk without personal protective equipment, as did her colleagues, but for future activities PPE against possible falling rocks and perhaps nesting birds is highly recommended. The loose sand was extremely difficult to work on and any walking put potential archaeological remains at great risk. Without a standard methodology on how to operate in such environments, Frigga Kruse decided to survey from the top downwards, thereby partially sliding down the slope and causing miniature landslides with each new step (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 The disturbed soil shows how the metal detector survey was conducted. Source: F. Kruse.

If done carefully, she could detect the ground in front of the landslides and place a survey flag before the loose sand rolled over the very spot. The starting location of the signal was deemed more important than the fact the metal object would now invariably move downslope. Again, careful movements achieved that the same object was not detected twice in the same transect. At the bottom of each transect, Kruse moved back up the slope via the already disturbed path and moved ‘the swing of a metal detector’ along to carry out the next transect. She felt this was a valid method, under the watchful eyes of Susan Barr, with which to conduct the metal detector survey.

Susan Barr being present, she temporarily overruled the prohibition to carry out any intrusive work. Marthe Koeweiden therefore opened a small evaluation trench in order to investigate site formation processes at this location. The small pit was inconclusive (Fig. 6), and it was decided not to open a bigger area.

Fig. 6 The small evaluation pit at the top of the slope was inconclusive. Source: F. Kruse.

Meanwhile, Frits Steenhuisen had arrived on site. He and Marthe Koeweiden now turned their attention to the dGPS and conducted a topographic survey. The main topographic features were the general lie of the land, the heavily eroded cliff, the various gullies, as well as the beach, which was further divided into high water, medium water, and low water lines.

Towards evening, tasks were divided anew. Marthe Koeweiden and Keechy Akkerman, a biogeologist from Utrecht University, now opened the first half of a small evaluation trench (110 cm x 72 cm x 60 cm) in Area 2 with the objective to investigate the wood that was protruding from the section. The evaluation was done in two halves for several reasons: firstly, a narrower width was thought to prevent the collapse of the profile, which consisted of very loose sand; secondly, the spoil was piled onto the half to be excavated next in order to stop it from sliding down the slope and facilitate backfilling; lastly, an attempt was made to prevent any wood found from being exposed unnecessarily long and probably drying out and being damaged further. Since this trench could not be finished in time, a thin layer of sand was left on the remains to be removed in the morning.

Fig. 7 Results of the second metal detector survey in Area 2. Source: F. Kruse.

Meanwhile, Frits Steenhuisen and Frigga Kruse used the dGPS to measure in the extents of Areas 1 and 2, the objects observed during the metal detectors surveys, as well as any points of interest marked previously. Once finished, the map will be included in Appendix 4.

Monday, August 18, 2014

Marthe Koeweiden assisted Keechy Akkerman for the day, so Frits Steenhuisen continued the evaluation trench in Area 2 (the second half measured 150 cm x 70 cm x 37 cm), while Frigga Kruse conducted a metal detector survey along the aforementioned lines in Area 3 (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 Results of the third metal detector survey in Area 3. Source: F. Kruse.

Upon conclusion of both the evaluation and the metal detecting, the new find spots were mapped using the dGPS. In addition, the ruined hunting hut was recorded but not in great detail. In light of the nearby memorial stone needing to be moved to a new, safer location in Kvalrossbukta, its current location was being recorded, but any material remains on the slopes above the site (originating from activities during and after World War Two) were not mapped.

As part of an multidisciplinary team of scientists, the archaeologists then turned their attention to studying the grass and the grazing on site as well as the presence of mosses and lichen. As a last act, they visited the whalers' graves at Hollanderhaugen in Kvalrossbukta but no archaeological work was undertaken here.

Other scientists soon began to arrive in the bay, which was the pickup point for the return to the 'Zeeland' at evening.

Tuesday, August 19, 2014

Louwrens Hacquebord, Susan Barr, Peter Jordan, Frigga Kruse, Frits Steenhuisen, and Marthe Koeweiden (along with other scientists of no immediate consequence to this report) were landed in Sørbukta. Splitting into teams of two, they spent an hour on a walkover of the bay. They then walked to Guineabukta and conducted a walkover of accessible beaches there, too. Lastly, they arrived in Titeltbukta and investigated the vast beach and the possible remains of a 17th century whaling station. Their progress can again be seen in the photographic record in Appendix 3.

Being aware of the research goals of other scientists, especially the bird ecologists, this hike again provided the team with opportunities to observe and report on natural phenomena outside their own specialisms.

Results and discussion

Louwrens Hacquebord had first visited Kvalrossbukta in 1983 and had since returned on a number of occasions. The same can be said for Susan Barr. The archaeological team benefitted immensely from their knowledge of a site that must have been teeming with archaeology, but at which little now seems to remain at the surface. The team, having no prior experience, was not disheartened and concentrated instead on the level of erosion at the site and on potential archaeology under the colluvium.

The map of the whaling station at Kvalrossbukta (Appendix 4) generated in the course of this project will be the most accurate to date. Currently, it is only possible to remark on the state of the erosion at the site of the former whaling station. According to aforementioned anecdotal evidence, this is immense and damaging to any archaeology. If the GPS survey were to be repeated in the near future, it would also be possible to say something about the rate of erosion of the cliff as well as the rate of change on the slope above, either through erosion in the gullies or the build-up of colluvium.

Having inspected the material remains of a former communication line and a former pipeline on the slopes above the site, Frigga Kruse and Marthe Koeweiden gained an invaluable insight into the characteristics and current state of decay of wood, metal, and concrete used in their construction. This was of importance because these remains get carried down the slope and onto the former whaling station, where they may either be mistaken for 'old' artefacts or mask the actual archaeology. The visual inspection showed that mistaking the wood and nails from above for anything else was barely possible. An understanding of the site's history since the whaling period (hunting/trapping, World War Two, the pipeline, the road construction, frequent (archaeological) visits, etc.) is essential to discern the site formation processes at work.

An investigation of the rockfaces above the site gave no clue as to the whaling period; if there had been any carvings, they had probably eroded out of the soft rock ages ago. Although more recent holes made by bullets were discovered, some with projectiles still remaining in them. Some had the appearance of being single shots; others looked like a machinegun volley. The usefulness of inspecting the rockface further lay in discovering heavily eroded nails at the same horizon at height in Area 1.

These nails in addition to some pieces of wood and several fragments of yellow and red brick had given rise to the metal detector survey in Area 1, which uncovered an additional handful of heavily corroded metal objects, in all likelihood also nails. The heavy corrosion was taken as a sign of 'old age', i.e. originating in the whaling period. So the question that remained was whether these relics could be related to the fort that is said to have stood at the edge of the bay or any other buildings nearby. If so, they are the last relics of these structures and this was probably the last time they were recorded. If not, an alternative explanation may be that all: wood, nails, bricks, were simply part of a fox trap that once stood here. To shed light on this problem, a small evaluation trench was opened, which mainly showed the build-up of colluvium at this location. The excavation stopped on the hint of a brown clayed layer. With hindsight, this should have been sampled for carbon contents and possible soil formation or compaction. Unfortunately, the team missed this chance.

Area 2 proved immediately promising with Marthe Koeweiden discovering a beautiful piece of 'Bartmann' ware on the eroded bank (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9 Marthe Koeweiden discovered this piece of Rhineland stoneware formerly used to contain alcoholic beverages. Source: F. Kruse.

Fig. 10 The evaluation uncovered part of a wooden floor under much colluvium. Source: F. Kruse.

The metal detector gave rise to many metal finds that pointed towards substantial construction activity at this location. To investigate if the protruding wooden planks were indeed structural: either a fallen roof or wall or a hidden floor, a small evaluation trench was opened that showed that the

wood was part of a former floor indeed (Fig. 10). Nails, charcoal, and the fragments of red earthenware remained very much in situ. In light of the limited intrusive work possible, the archaeological team thinks that a house of the whaling period once stood here and that much of it remains under the colluvium.

In the vicinity of the former hunting hut, it is difficult to draw conclusion about the whaling period. Much material such as bricks has been collected and reused here. Whaling remains are likely to be hidden under this secondary material and under the colluvium.

Area 3 was therefore intentionally placed at some distance from the hut although the metal detector survey was still greatly influenced by metal objects originating from the hunting activities. Again, protruding and heavily decaying wood coupled with heavily corroded nails and perhaps other metal objects gave rise to the idea that here, too, lies the hidden floor of a former hut worthwhile of investigating further.

Conspicuous at the site were a layer of fine yellow sand entirely untypical for the island and probably imported (as ballast?) as well as the presence of grass, and much of it (Fig. 11). If the grass seeds were not introduced by the whalers themselves then perhaps an increase in nutrients in the soil caused by whaling activities enhances the growth of grass to this day. This, too, is worth investigating.

Fig. 11 The lush grass on the site had been grazed by geese. Source: F. Kruse.

The surveys of Sørbukta, Guineabukta, and Titeltbukta were on the whole disappointing. In Sørbukta and Guineabukta, several cultural remains dating back to the hunting period were discovered. These included foxes traps, including one for live foxes (Fig. 12), and a possible fox cage.

Fig. 12 A fox trap, now cultural heritage. Source: F. Kruse.

Fig. 13 A possible whaling station in Titeltbukta? Source: F. Kruse.

In Titeltbukta, driftwood had been arranged in such a fashion as to suggest house platforms. This idea was strengthened by the presence of several century-old Dutch bricks (Fig. 13). Yet, the metal detector survey only gave rise to two fairly recent nails. Based on the latter, the site is not a very convincing candidate for a former whaling station, but it, too, could be studied in more detail. In its

favour were the presence of several large whale bones, the phosphorus of which by now supported sizable mounds of lush vegetation. If there were signs of slaughter on the bones, these were in fact hidden by the plants.

Conclusion and further work

Although the remains of the former whaling station in Kvalrossbukta had until recently been much richer (according to anecdotes), the archaeological team found plenty of evidence that much may yet be covered by colluvium. In view that this site would be a valuable comparison to the work done by Louwrens Hacquebord in Smeerenburg in Svalbard and that the site is highly threatened by erosion by the sea, the archaeological team suggests a thorough desk-based assessment including a comparison of all known historical sources and depictions as well as a compilation of all previous archaeological visits and works. They further suggest a large-scale rescue excavation of the site.

During a rescue excavation particular attention should be paid to the following:

- Using an excavation strategy applicable to very loose sand
- Using personal protective equipment (PPE) to operate in the Arctic, in bad weather (which the archaeological team was luck not to have this time), under unstable rockfaces with soft rock, and in the vicinity of breeding birds
- There is no freshwater on or near the site
- The normal tidal range is not a problem to archaeological work
- Carrying out a follow-up dGPS survey to investigate the rate of erosion/topographic change
- Excavating all locations where decaying wood is protruding from the sections both in the cliff but also in the gullies
- Finding the remaining extent of any structures as though to be able to say anything about extent of the whole site as well as arrangement, size, and construction of individual buildings
- Excavating the conspicuous grassy areas
- Keeping in mind any multidisciplinary research, e.g. taking vegetation samples, taking sediment samples, etc
- Excavating Hollanderhaugen: this would not be a rescue excavation as Hollanderhaugen is not presently at risk, but it would address pressing questions such as whether the

seven overwinterers were buried here and what the demography of the whaling station was

- Excavating at Titeltbukta in order to proof whether or not the observed features were part of a former whaling station

The archaeological team of the Arctic Centre at the University of Groningen would very much welcome it if they could play a part in future proceedings. They will in any case be glad to answer any queries third parties may have and support any new projects that may arise from this.

Location of archive

The archaeological materials compiled during the Jan Mayen Expedition 2014 mainly comprise written documents, the photographic record and index, and the digital map of Kvalrossbukta. Copies of this report as well as all supporting documents and the indexed digital photographs remain both with the author and at the Arctic Centre of the University of Groningen.

Prior to the fieldwork, Susan Barr had collected some surface finds. Together with the stoneware sherd, they were brought to the Norwegian station and are kept there.

This interim archaeological report was disseminated to G. J. van den Dam on behalf of the Royal Netherlands Navy, to Susan Barr on behalf of the Directorate of Cultural Heritage, and to the County Governor of Nordland.

Any publications to arise as a result of this project will also be disseminated to the above representatives and to the scientists of the expedition.

References

- Arctisch Centrum & WBPI, Wetenschappelijk plan
- County Governor of Nordland (2014) 'Letter to Royal Netherlands Navy, 11 July'
- Deployment order Jan Mayen Expedition 2014, CTG 428.05 (COMNLMASRFOR), Date of issue: 09 JUL 14

On behalf of the archaeological team on the Jan Mayen Expedition 2014,

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of several overlapping, fluid strokes that form a stylized, somewhat abstract shape.

Dr. Frigga Kruse

Arctic Centre, University of Groningen

March 10, 2015

APPENDIX 1

Expedition planning

A1.1

Jan Mayen 2014

Archaeology Schedule, version 140704

NOTE:

This schedule is aimed at high flexibility yet maximum research output. The archaeology team hopes to achieve this by being dropped at Kvalrossbukta and using this as a base for three days. We envisage walking to all sites in the vicinity. We are asking for a zodiac transfer to the south of the island on 18 August. If daily planning permits, we hope to have access to a zodiac on other occasions and make landings in other areas not mentioned in this document. We look forward to the cooperation with the Navy, the Media, and all other scientists.

Week 32	Load in Den Helder Date and time to be arrange with the Navy
11 August	Leaving from Den Helder 9am on board, 10am sailing
14 August	Arriving at the Norwegian station at Jan Mayen Welcome and time to discuss fieldwork details with the Norwegians Probably overland transfer to Kvalrossbukta to set up camp Probably no time for fieldwork
15 August	Full day at Kvalrossbukta Full archaeological team (four people) Tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Site reconnaissance to decide on and sketch features and portable finds (full team)- GPS base/rover survey of features and finds (Frigga and Frits)- GPS base/rover survey of topography (probably Frigga and Frits)- Full description of features and finds, including preservation and threats (Peter and Marthe)- Digital photography of features and finds (Peter)- Metal detecting (Marthe)
16 August	Full day at Kvalrossbukta Full team Tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Continuation of GPS base/rover survey (Frigga and Frits)- Continuation of metal detecting (Frits)- Scale drawings of key features and finds (probably Frigga)- Contact temperature and thermal image of material remains (Peter, Marthe) Options: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Identification of human impact on local environment

- Short coastal walk south towards Antarcticberget, using handhelds (Peter and student)
- Start of coastal walk north along Haugenstranda towards Maria Muschbukta, using handhelds (Peter and student, pick-up on route?)

- 17 August Full day at Kvalrossbukta
Split teams
Tasks:
- GPS base/rover survey may need to be finished (Frigga and Frits)
 - Coastal walk northwards towards along Haugenstranda towards Maria Muschbukta, using handhelds (Peter and student, pick-up north of Nordlaguna?)
- [Return to ship]
- 18 August Full day at Guineabukta AND/OR Titeltbukta
Probably split teams
Rapid reconnaissance
Tasks:
- GPS mapping of all material remains (team 1 with the GPS base/rover; team 2 with a handheld GPS)
 - Full description and digital photography of all material remains
 - Sketching of key features
- 19 August Length on site unclear
Departure time unclear
Options:
- Kokksletta
 - Southern shore, e.g. Jamesonbukta
- 22 August Arrive in Edinburgh ca. 2pm
Option to fly out
- 26 August Leave Edinburgh ca 8am,
Arrival in Den Helder

To do:

FK/MK: Write archaeological briefing for non-archaeologists

Prepare a small presentation for on board

Receive biological briefing

VU - VERY USEFUL
 NU - NOT USED

ADD: GREY DUCT TAPE
 RUBBER BANDS
 BLACK MARKER

ARCHAEOLOGY EQUIPMENT LIST

Jan Mayen, August 10 - 25, 2014

PRE-SITE

- Project Design
- RA & Safety Measures
- Site Manual
- VU Site Plan, FK MK
- NU digital map, FS
- VU Site File, background info, MK
- NU clip board, FK
- VU notebook / diary ALL
- NU paper, FK

SETTING OUT

- Service Plans
- CAT Scan
- Tapes 100m
- Tapes 50m
- VU Tapes 30m
- sledge hammer, mallet
- pegs
- arrows
- spray paint

SUB-CONTRACT/HIRE

- Magnetometry
- Resistivity
- Radar
- Topo. Survey
- Building Recording
- Photogrammetry
- JCB
- Bowser

EXCAVATION

- spade, shovel
- mattock, pick
- sweeping brush
- cutters, snips
- Dutch hoe
- VU trowel, FK
- VU 1 hand shovel, FS
- hand brush
- bucket
- wheel barrow
- kneeling mat
- VU waterproof bags
- VU ziplock bags
- ~~metal rod~~
- NU dowsing rods

RECORDING

- NU pro forma, FK
- VU (H) camera, digital, ALL *danger*
- camera, slide + films
- camera, colour + films
- VU camera, B&W + films
- VU N arrow, FK
- [NU] compass, FK
- ranging poles 2m
- VU ranging poles 1m, FK
- VU scales 30cm, 10cm, FK
- NU Nobo board & letters, FK
- NU chalk board & chalk, FK
- VU 1 tripod, FS
- ladder
- dumpy level
- staff 5m
- water spray can

DRAWING

- planning frame 20cm
- planning frame 5cm
- tape 10m
- VU tape 8m
- tape 3m
- string and nails
- plumb bob
- spirit level
- drawing board
- NU permatrace, FK
- NU graphpaper, FK
- NU masking tape, FK
- VU pencil, eraser, sharpener, FK
- VU scale ruler, FK

SAMPLING

- floatation tank (rubber gloves)
- sieves
- tubs, lids, stickers
- VU bags, ties, labels, FK
- bowls
- brushes, toothbrushes

H&S

- signs, hazard tape
- barriers, road pins
- herras fencing
- PPE
- (H) First Aid Box, FK
- (H) Wet Wipes, ALL

WELFARE

- container
- loo
- washing facilities
- van (fuel card, oil, screen wash)
- (H) mobile & charger, ALL

OTHER

- VU *SURVEY FLAG*
- VU 1 metal detector, FK
- plywood sheet
- plastic sheeting
- hammer
- saw
- crowbar
- eye protection
- fuel (petrol, paraffin)
- NU contact thermometer, FK
- NU ? thermal camera, ML
- NU *TOOTHPICK*

- batteries AAA, AA
- batteries lithium, 9V
- ~~battery charger~~
- torch
- whistle
- ~~sun screen~~
- VU laptop, FS
- VU life vests, Navy
- VU survival suits, Navy

- gun
- NU 2 radio, Navy
- signal pistol / - pen / flares
- trip wire with flares
- other bear deterrents
- handheld GPS
- ~~2 handheld PDA, FK~~
- VU 1 GPS rover/base, FK
- Satellite phone
- distress beacon

If found, please return to:

Arctic Centre, Aweg 30, 9718 CW Groningen, NL

Personal equipment

- Stay dry (especially in the zodiacs and on landing)
- Stay warm in the field and in bed
- Stay safe

Tent camp

- ✓ 2 Arctic Centre tents, 2 pers, FK and MK to share one (bring ear plugs!)
- ✓ 1 tent FS, 2 pers
- ✓ 1 tent PJ, 2 pers
- 4 ground sheets, FS to buy
- ✓ FK, FS, PJ: own sleeping bags and mats
- ✓ MK to ~~either~~ use AC sleeping bag and mat ~~or buy own~~

Cooking

- ✓ FS and PJ to bring a stove each
- ✓ FS uses petroleum
- ✓ PJ uses butane
- ✓ Enough fuel to cook for 4 people 3x daily for 5 + 2 days
- ✓ PJ to bring pans
- ✓ PJ to bring kettle
- ✓ ALL to bring own cup, (deep) plate, cutlery
- FK to bring dish washing stuff *bowl!*
- ✓ ALL to bring own toilet paper
- ✓ FS to bring small shovel
- ✓ FK to look up camping requirements for Spitsbergen — *permittion received*

Food

- ✓ FS to buy Bever meals: 4 peoples' dinner and desert for 5 + 2 days
- ✓ FK to buy ~~30-24~~ bottles of drinking water nearer to time
- ✓ MK to arrange breakfast and lunch for 4 people for 5 + 2 days (keep in mind how packages store, keep dry, open, re-seal, re-package; ask FS for input)

Voedsel expeditie Jan Mayen

„Brood”

- Brinta 2 x 500g
- Roggebrood 3 x 500g
- Knäckebröd 4 x
- Cream crackers 2 x 200g
- Zweedse broodjes 2 x 200g

PLANNED FOR
4 PEOPLE → HEALTHY DAILY
[+2] PAY
→ IS ACTUAL FACT, THE
TEAM ONLY CAMPED
FOR 2 NIGHT

Beleg

- Margarine 1 x 500g
- Kaas, belegen 1 x 500g
- Philadelphia 2 x
- Leverpastei 6 x 56g
- Luncheon Meat 2 x 200g
- Makreel in Tomatensaus 2 x 125g
- Metworst 1 x 400g
- Pindakaas 1 x 650g
- Hazelnootpasta 1 x 400g
- Jam 1 x 84g
- Honing, beetje

Drank

- Melkpoeder 7 x 245g (14 liter melk)
- Oploskoffie 1 x 200g (120 koppen)
- Thee 3 x doosje (Westminster, pepermint, kruiden)
- Hot chocolate/chocolademelk
- Limonade, bosvruchten 1 x
- Tuinkruidenbouillon 1 x 140g

Snacks

- Droge worst 3 x 240g (6 stuks)
- Notenmix 3 x 250g
- Pringles 3 x bus
- Verkade Chocolade: 2 x melk, 2 x puur, 2 x hazelnoot (180g)
- Mini Babybel 10 x
- Perziken 1 x blik

Overig

- Zout & peper
- Toiletpapier 4 x rol
- Vuilniszakken
- Afwasmiddel, 10 schuurspons, 3x theedoek, 2x vaatdoek
- Snijplank 2 x klein
- Plastic kommen 4 x
- Bestek, doos + schaar

- Diverse kleine plastic doosjes

Frigga (van thuis)

- Kaasschaaf
- Blikopener
- Mes
- Suiker
- Afwasteil
- + fantasie van de expeditiekok

APPENDIX 2

Maps and plans

A2.1 Map of Jan Mayen

A2.2 Map of Båtvika

A2.3 Map of Kvalrossbukta

A2.4 Map of Titeltbukta

FIG.6. KVALROSSBUKTA, Jan Mayen.
Restanten van walvisvaardershuisen.
(situatie juni 1983)

Beschrijving van locaties:

- 1+2 gelegen op de puinhelling. chaotische toestand van 2 walviskaken, wervels, stukken hout, en 1 gele baksteen.
 - 3 over een breedte van 5 meter steken planken recht uit de brink (recht onder gedenksteen)
 - 4 uit de brink steken twee walviskaken met daartussen restanten van 2 opstaande houten wanden. (afstand tussen walviskaken ong. 5 m. Links en rechts van de kaken steken ook nog enkele vloerplanken uit de brink)
 - 5 enkele onduidelijke planken tussen 2 moddergeulen
 - 6 over ruim dertig meter steken stukken planken uit de bovenkant van de brink en er liggen gele (+ wat rode) baksteenfragmenten. De zuidpunt heeft naast vloerdelen ook enkele opstaande planken, waartussen een ronde compacte massa van zaagsel ligt.
 - 7 uit een klein stukje brink tussen 2 moddergeulen steken kleine stukjes van planken
 - 8 over een lengte van ruim 25 meter steken vloerdelen uit de brink. de hele omgeving is bezaaid met stukken gele baksteen. Er is zo te zien al eens gegraven; de zuidkant van de brink is althans kunstmatig met een boomstam gestut. (schoorsteenmantel en muurdelen van het "Museet" zijn met gele bakstenen gebouwd!). Onder een laag (vloer?)planken midden in de brink van 8 was een laag geel zand herkenbaar (absoluut niet afkomstig van Jan Mayen) en enkele vierkante blokken turf. Zeer veel nagels rollen uit de brink.
 - 9 enkele onduidelijke planken steken uit de brink.
- ("Museet": gebouwd in WOII, en een tijdje in gebruik geweest als museumpje voor walvisvaart-restanten. Deels gebouwd met materialen van de oude huizen(zie 8). Bij het graven van een geul rond dit museet werden ook daar in de grond gele baksteen fragmenten en een stuk pijpstaal gevonden)
- (Gedenksteen: in 1930 door Nederlandse expeditie geplaatst met tekst: Outgert Jacobsz.
van Grootebroek
en zijne
6 Hollandsche makers
zijn in april 1934 hier
bezwegen bij eene poging
tot overwintering.)

(strand: nergens zijn ook maar enige restanten van eventuele traanovens te vinden; ook niet bij kijken vanaf de top van Kvalrossen. De strandwallen zijn ook erg mobiel en bedekt met aangespoelde boomstammen en grote keien)

(= locatie grondmonster; zie hfdst 6.)

Figure 8.4: Remains of the 17th century Dutch whaling stations in Kvalrossbukta on Jan Mayen in 1983. Drawing: L. Hacquebord en H. Waterbolk.

A2.7 Map of Sørbukta

APPENDIX 3

Photographic record

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1050314	Den Helder, ZR MS Zeeland (left) at Stijger 17	FK, 13/08/14
Digital	P1050321	At sea, zodiacs being readied aboard the 'Zeeland'	FK, 15/08/14
Digital	P1050328	Jan Mayen, first view of the Beerenberg, calm sea, low clouds, occasional drizzle, looking N	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050333	Jan Mayen, the Norwegian station on the southern shore, looking NW	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050334	Jan Mayen, the Norwegian station on the southern shore, looking N	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050337	Tronfjellet (?) to the SW of the Norwegian station, looking W	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050343	Batvika, the archaeological team from left to right: Marthe Koeweiden, Keechy Akkerman, Frits Steenhuisen, Peter Jordan, Frigga Kruse. Keechy is a biogeologist from Utrecht University who joined the team for logistical purposes. To the right Stefan Blaas of the Marines (green uniform) and the Norwegian station commander Rob (blue beret).	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050345	Batvika, the archaeological team from left to right: Marthe Koeweiden, Keechy Akkerman, Frits Steenhuisen, Peter Jordan, Frigga Kruse. Keechy is a biogeologist from Utrecht University who joined the team for logistical purposes. To the right Stefan Blaas and Gerrit-Jan van Dam.	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050346	Batvika, the archaeological team from left to right: Marthe Koeweiden, Keechy Akkerman, Frits Steenhuisen, Peter Jordan, Frigga Kruse. Keechy is a biogeologist from Utrecht University who joined the team for logistical purposes. To the right the station commander.	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050348	Kvalrossbukta, the archaeological team is joined by the media team, Louwrens Hacquebord, and Susan Barr for a reconnaissance of the former whaling station. Peter is carrying the GPS case, Marthe the tripod.	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050349	Kvalrossbukta, Louwrens, Koliijn (media), Frits, Keechy, Marthe, and Susan. To the left, the 'new' cross of Hollanderhaugen is just visible above the rails. Looking S.	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050356	Kvalrossbukta, Frits setting up the GPS base station near the hunting hut 'Haugenhytta' aka 'Museet', looking S	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050357	Kvalrossbukta, Frits setting up the GPS base station near the hunting hut 'Haugenhytta' aka 'Museet', looking S	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050358	Kvalrossbukta, remains of the hunting hut 'Haugenhytta' aka 'Museet' under Kvalrossen, looking W towards Grønknapp	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050360	Kvalrossbukta, inconclusive plank of wood wedged between rocks under Kvalrossen where the rockface meets the colluvium: a reminder that wood may have come from above (apparently, planks formerly rimed the well on top)	FK, 16/08/14

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Digital	P1050361	Kvalrossbukta, Haugenhytta and to the right of it the GPS base station, the yellow flags mark points of interest after the reconnaissance, looking NW	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050363	Kvalrossbukta, view out to sea, the tidal range was more than a meter with low water at about 14:30, looking SW	FK, 16/08/14
Digital	P1050370	Kvalrossbukta, archaeological camp, kitchen tend and eating area in the centre, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050371	Kvalrossbukta, many large whalebones (including those that eroded out of the site in a storm in 2010) have been taken to the hut 'Puppenby'	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050372	Kvalrossbukta, wood on the eroding slopes originates from a former pipeline as well as a telephone line, looking N	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050373	Kvalrossbukta, wood on the eroding slopes originates from a former pipeline as well as a telephone line, looking N	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050374	Kvalrossbukta, close-up of a wooden construction (pipeline or telephone line?) with view on investigating the type and state of decay of both wood and metal in order to tell it apart from older remains	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050375	Kvalrossbukta, close-up of a wooden construction (pipeline or telephone line?) with view on investigating the type and state of decay of both wood and metal in order to tell it apart from older remains	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050376	Kvalrossbukta, close-up of a wooden construction (pipeline or telephone line?) with view on investigating the type and state of decay of both wood and metal in order to tell it apart from older remains	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050377	Kvalrossbukta, close-up of a wooden construction (pipeline or telephone line?) with view on investigating the type and state of decay of both wood and metal in order to tell it apart from older remains	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050378	Kvalrossbukta, cow (?) bone found near memorial stone (moved to Hollanderhaugen on 20/08/14), was the end broken or cut?, serves as a reminder of the different periods: whaling, hunting/trapping, WWII, recent - and that the bone may have arrived at any time	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050379	Kvalrossbukta, cow (?) bone found near memorial stone (moved to Hollanderhaugen on 20/08/14), was the end broken or cut?, serves as a reminder of the different periods: whaling, hunting/trapping, WWII, recent - and that the bone may have arrived at any time	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050380	Kvalrossbukta, recent wood constructions (pipeline or telephone line?) on the slope above the former whaling station, note the central concrete block, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050381	Kvalrossbukta, recent wood constructions (pipeline or telephone line?) on the slope above the former whaling station, the concrete block marks the construction of the pipeline in 1959, looking NE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050382	Kvalrossbukta, the concrete block on the slope above the former whaling station marks the construction of the pipeline in 1959. The six workers were S.S., H.S., D.K., ?P., S.P., and H.F.	FK, 17/08/14

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Digital	P1050383	Kvalrossbukta, in search of the former 'fort', looking W towards Grønknapp	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050384	While searching the rockface for signs of human activity (carvings, bullet holes), I found three heavily corroded metal objects (probably nails) at height (see three yellow flags in a row); the slope also revealed wood as well as yellow and red brick fragments, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050385	While searching the rockface for signs of human activity (carvings, bullet holes), I found three heavily corroded metal objects (probably nails) at height (see three yellow flags in a row); the slope also revealed wood as well as yellow and red brick fragments, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050387	Below the rockface, I found heavily corroded metal objects (probably nails) as well as yellow and red brick fragments, scale 20cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050388	Below the rockface was a singular wooden plank sticking out of the colluvium; there were a handful of other wood fragments	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050389	Below the rockface, a yellow brick fragment	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050390	Below the rockface, yellow and red brick fragments	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050391	Below the rockface, a heavily corroded metal object (probably a nail), scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050392	Below the rockface, a yellow brick fragment	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050393	Below the rockface, a fragment of a beach cobble, was it used for anything? Scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050394	Below the rockface, at height, three heavily corroded metal objects (probably nails) in a row, scale 50cm (white segment only)	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050395	Below the rockface, close-up of first (from left) corroded metal object, scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050396	Below the rockface, between the three nails in a row, a red brick, scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050397	Below the rockface, close-up of second (from left) corroded metal object, scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050398	Below the rockface, close-up of third (from left) corroded metal object, scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050399	Below the rockface, immediately right of the three nails in a row, a red brick fragment, some layering in the colluvium, scale 30 cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050400	Below the rockface, immediately right of the three nails in a row, some layering in the colluvium	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050401	To the left and right of the rockface were rockfalls and mass flow; some of the cobbles and boulders had the appearance of red brick but usually contained many gas bubbles	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050402	Below the rockface, above the three nails in a row, some layering in the colluvium, some plant growth on the colluvium, scale 50cm (red only)	FK, 17/08/14

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Digital	P1050411	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, the first plank of wood to stick out of the section (at right angles) when approaching from the north, looking NE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050412	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, a piece of highly decorated pottery discovered by Marthe	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050413	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, a piece of highly decorated pottery discovered by Marthe, scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050414	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, the yellow flag to the left marks the find location of the above pottery; about 50cm below the ranging rods, wooden planks stick out of the section (at right angles), scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050415	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, the yellow flag to the left marks the find location of the above pottery; about 50cm below the ranging rods, wooden planks stick out of the section (at right angles), scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050416	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, wooden planks stick out of the section at right angles, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050417	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, wooden planks stick out of the section at right angles, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050418	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, the change from moist to dry may mark the position of covered wooden planks, this may be a good area for a test pit, more wooden planks right of centre confirm this, looking NE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050419	Kvalrossbukta, view along the beach and cliff, Haugenhytta, base station, and patches of brick fragments clearly visible, all yellow flag mark areas and objects of interest, looking SE	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050420	Kvalrossbukta, below Haugenhytta, it is difficult to discern whaling and hunting activities, some of the wood may date back to the whaling period, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050421	Kvalrossbukta, below Haugenhytta, Dutch brick were collected here for reuse and have since been broken by freeze-thaw action	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050422	Kvalrossbukta, below Haugenhytta, Dutch brick were collected here for reuse and have since been broken by freeze-thaw action	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050423	Kvalrossbukta, below Haugenhytta, nails are very (!) frequent, the assumption is that heavily corroded metal objects and square nails date to the whaling period, scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050424	Kvalrossbukta, below Haugenhytta, decaying wood that protruded from the section, commonly at right angles, was thought to date from the whaling period; near the hut, it could be masked by more recent wood	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050425	Kvalrossbukta, near Haugenhytta, some pieces of wood were less indicative than others, usually because of lack of orientation	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050426	Kvalrossbukta, near Haugenhytta, decaying wood	FK, 17/08/14

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Site: Jan Mayen Expedition, 13 - 25 August 2014			
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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1050434	Kvalrossbukta, decaying wood, scale 30cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050435	Kvalrossbukta, decaying wood, scale 30cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050436	Kvalrossbukta, is this structural wood on this bulge of colluvium?, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050437	Kvalrossbukta, is this structural wood on this bulge of colluvium?, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050438	Kvalrossbukta, does the dry horizon again mark hidden wood?, note the planks of wood protruding from the section immediately below both ends of the ranging rod, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050439	Kvalrossbukta, close-up of wooden planks protruding from the section, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050440	Kvalrossbukta, yellow flags mark decaying wood protruding from the section	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050441	Kvalrossbukta, decaying wood, scale 30cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050442	Kvalrossbukta, at the left end of the ranging rod, wooden planks protrude from the section; yellow flags mark decaying wood in the section, note the red brick fragment, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050443	Kvalrossbukta, wooden plank that eroded out of the section, note the large nails, scale 30cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050444	Kvalrossbukta, close-up of a large nail, scale 10cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050445	Kvalrossbukta, another wooden plank that eroded out of the section, again note the nails, scale 30cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050446	Kvalrossbukta, wood eroding out of the section, scale 30cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050447	Kvalrossbukta, wood eroding out of the section, note the layering in the colluvium, scale 30cm	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050448	Kvalrossbukta, structural wood? A barrel?	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050449	Kvalrossbukta, structural wood? A barrel? Note the retained moisture around the wood.	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050458	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, Keechy and Marthe excavating, Frits recording as film and photo	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050459	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, Keechy and Marthe excavating, Frits recording as film and photo	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050460	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, evaluation trench in broader context	FK, 17/08/14
Digital	P1050464	Kvalrossbukta, the excavation is proceeding, looking SW towards Antarcticberget	FK, 17/08/14

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Site: Jan Mayen Expedition, 13 - 25 August 2014			Sheet <u>6</u> of <u>11</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1050483	Kvalrossbukta, below grassy patch, the evaluation unearthed a wooden 'floor', an irregular piece of wood along the right trench edge, several nails, and pieces of charcoal; all appeared to lie on the 'floor', scale 30cm	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050484	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, the evaluation have rise to a section of colluvium without many notable features; there appears to be a brown layer of 2 or 3 cm just above the 'floor', scale 30 cm	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050485	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, the evaluation gave rise to a wooden 'floor' with in-situ finds such as nails and charcoal, the section of colluvium has few features but maybe there is a thin brown layer just above the 'floor', scales 30cm and 1m	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050486	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, evaluation, close-up of the nails, scale 30cm	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050487	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, evaluation, close-up of the piece of wood and the nails, scale 30cm	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050488	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, evaluation, close-up of a nail and some pieces of charcoal, scale 30cm	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050489	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, evaluation, close-up of a nail and some pieces of charcoal, scale 30cm	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050490	Kvalrossbukta, site of 3. metal detector survey, setting out the grid, based on beach cobbles at bottom and line of decaying wood (yellow flags) at the top	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050491	Kvalrossbukta, vicinity of Haugenhytta, yellow brick fragment comprising bivalve shell	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050492	Kvalrossbukta, vicinity of Haugenhytta, yellow brick fragment comprising bivalve shell	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050493	Kvalrossbukta, vicinity of Haugenhytta, yellow brick fragment comprising possible fingerprints (?)	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050494	Kvalrossbukta, vicinity of Haugenhytta, complete red brick (see dimensions in notebook)	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050495	Kvalrossbukta, vicinity of Haugenhytta, reuse of yellow brick, again fallen out of use	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050497	Kvalrossbukta, vicinity of Haugenhytta, reuse of bricks, again fallen out of use	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050498	Kvalrossbukta, 3. survey, detections at the end of survey, the two meters at the top (which include the line of decaying wood) were only surveyed visually because of too many finds, where the slope breaks the detecting began in earnest	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050499	Kvalrossbukta, 3. survey, detections at the end of survey, the two meters at the top (which include the line of decaying wood) were only surveyed visually because of too many finds, where the slope breaks the detecting began in earnest	FK, 18/08/14

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1050509	Kvalrossbukta, view towards Antarticherget, looking SW	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050512	Haugenstranda as seen from the road (not visited), looking towards the Beerenberg, looking NE	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050513	Haugenstranda as seen from the road (not visited), looking towards the Beerenberg, looking NE	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050516	A second concrete block denoting the building of the pipeline in 1959, four men, four handprints and sets of initials	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050517	A close-up of the second concrete block showing that the handprints were made wearing gloves	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050519	Kvalrossbukta, walking from the road to the site, looking SW	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050521	Kvalrossbukta, walking from the road to the site, note, the GPS base station and Haugenhytta, looking SW	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050522	Kvalrossbukta, detail of Haugenhytta, the use of birch bark as insulating material, the sheets are so big and uniform they had to be brought to the island (i.e. no driftwood)	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050523	Kvalrossbukta, detail of Haugenhytta, the use of birch bark as insulating material, the sheets are so big and uniform they had to be brought to the island (i.e. no driftwood)	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050524	Kvalrossbukta, detail of Haugenhytta, the use of birch bark as insulating material, the sheets are so big and uniform they had to be brought to the island (i.e. no driftwood)	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050525	Kvalrossbukta, the rock in the wall of Haugenhytta shows that rockfall is a serious problem on site	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050526	Kvalrossbukta, Haugenhytta, note the heavy use of nails, no wonder the metal detector goes mad on a hunting site like this	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050527	Kvalrossbukta, detail of haugenhytta, reused yellow bricks around the stove protecting the hut from catching fire	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050528	Kvalrossbukta, under the pile of collected and broken brick and some decaying wood is a layer of peculiar yellow sand	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050529	Kvalrossbukta, below the grassy patch, once the evaluation was completed, the trench was backfilled	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050530	Kvalrossbukta, details of the green grassy patch, signs of grazing by geese	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050533	Kvalrossbukta, details of the grassy patch, goose droppings	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050536	Kvalrossbukta, details of the green grassy patch, signs of grazing by geese	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050537	Kvalrossbukta, the only orange lichen to be seen here	FK, 18/08/14
Digital	P1050539	Kvalrossbukta, view towards Kvalrossen, looking N	FK, 18/08/14

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Site: Jan Mayen Expedition, 13 - 25 August 2014			Sheet <u>8</u> of <u>11</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1050550	Sørbukta, approaching the landing point, Ronden and Sørvestkapp to the right, looking SE	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050551	Sørbukta, Ronden and Sørvestkapp in the background, bleak beach with driftwood and bone, looking S	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050552	Sørbukta, broad beach, lava field, edge of vegetation, looking E	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050553	Sørbukta, looking N	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050554	Sørbukta, driftwood, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050555	Sørbukta, driftwood	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050556	Sørbukta, driftwood	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050557	Sørbukta, whale bone, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050558	Sørbukta, whale bone, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050559	Sørbukta, whale bone	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050560	Sørbukta, whale bone, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050561	Sørbukta, whale bone, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050561	Sørbukta, whale bone, is this a sign of being worked?	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050563	Sørbukta, whale bone, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050564	Sørbukta, driftwood at right angles to the sea, looking S	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050565	Sørbukta, broken life ring, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050568	Sørbukta, plant in a glass bottle	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050569	Sørbukta, driftwood, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050570	Sørbukta, volcanic formation	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050571	Sørbukta, driftwood	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050572	Sørbukta, whale bone, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14

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Digital	P1050583	Sørbukta, whale bone, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050584	Sørbukta, whale bone (not a vertebra for once), scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050586	Sørbukta, whale bone	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050592	Sørbukta, intended? A seat? A toilet?	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050597	Sørbukta, leaving the bay and walking across a very mossy lava field en route to Guineabukta	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050598	en route	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050604	en route	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050605	en route, looking back towards Sørbukta, looking S	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050615	a small bay en route to Guineabukta; it appeared pointless to climb down in search for cultural remains, looking SW	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050616	en route, looking towards Guineabukta, looking NE	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050618	en route, a fox trap, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050619	Guineabukta, loose boulders on the beach wall, much driftwood behind, looking N	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050621	Guineabukta, typical assemblage of driftwood, or is it? looking E	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050622	Guineabukta, in this driftwood an orderly pile of wood, a fox cage as Susan suggested?, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050623	Guineabukta, orderly pile of driftwood, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050624	Guineabukta, loose boulders, awful to walk on terrible to land, looking N	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050625	Guineabukta, a fox trap, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050626	Guineabukta, Louwrens found a message in a (plastic) bottle from the Faroes dated 2011 (?)	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050627	Guineabukta, brackish lagoon, grass, grazing by geese, goose droppings	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050628	Guineabukta, grass, grazing by geese, goose droppings	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050629	Guineabukta, brackish lagoon, grass, grazing by geese, goose droppings	FK, 19/08/14

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1050643	en route to Titeltbukta	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050644	en route to Titeltbukta, this looks waaay easier than it way, saw a Snowy Owl here	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050646	en route to Titeltbukta, terrible walking on lava	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050647	en route to Titeltbukta, terrible walking on lava	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050648	Titeltbukta, arriving, looking NE	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050649	Titeltbukta, broad sandy beach, looking NE	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050650	Titeltbukta with small hunting hut, does the driftwood protect the remains of a former whaling station? Looking E	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050651	Titeltbukta, whaling station?	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050652	Titeltbukta, do the logs mark a building platform? Scale 1m, looking E	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050653	Titeltbukta, logs appear to lie at right angles to each other, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050654	Titeltbukta, logs appear to lie at right angles to each other, note the assemblage of bricks, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050655	Titeltbukta, an assemblage of Dutch bricks, no context, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050656	Titeltbukta, close-up of the assemblage of bricks, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050657	Titeltbukta, are these right angles coincidence or intensional? Scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050658	Titeltbukta, was there a whaling station below the small hunting hut? Scale 1m, looking W	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050660	Titeltbukta, there appear to be some upright posts	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050661	Titeltbukta, an upright post?	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050662	Titeltbukta, whale bone among the remains, no immediate signs of working, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050663	Titeltbukta, whale bone giving off phosphorus thereby enhancing vegetation growth, scale 1m	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050665	Titeltbukta, whale bone giving off phosphorus thereby enhancing vegetation growth, looking N	FK, 19/08/14
Digital	P1050666	Titeltbukta, whale bone giving off phosphorus, looking N	FK, 19/08/14

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Digital	P1050683	Båtvika, Expedition HQ	FK, 20/08/14
Digital	P1050684	Tronfjellet (?) to the SW of the Norwegian station, looking SW	FK, 20/08/14
Digital	P1050688	Tronfjellet (?) to the SW of the Norwegian station, looking SW	FK, 20/08/14
Digital	P1050690	Beerenberg, in its usual cloud cover, looking N	FK, 21/08/14
Digital	P1050692	Zeeland' leaving Jan Mayen, looking back	FK, 21/08/14

APPENDIX 4

Digital map of Kvalrossbukta

A4.1 Map of archaeological remains in Kvalrossbukta

A4.2 Comparison 1983 and 2014

A4.3 Comparison 1983 and 2014

